

**ILMIY VA
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**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
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THERAPY**

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ТЕРАПИЯ

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WHAT IS MAGNESIUM AND WHAT ROLE DOES IT PLAY IN THE BODY?

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Abstract. Magnesium is an important macronutrient for human health. It is involved in many vital processes of the body, for example, it supports the functioning of the cardiovascular and nervous systems. Magnesium deficiency negatively affects performance and quality of life. Due to its deficiency, concentration decreases, a feeling of fatigue appears, and general well-being worsens.

Keywords: magnesium, organism, microelement, metabolism, ischemic heart disease.

In the human body, the amount of magnesium is approximately 20-28 g - mostly inside the cells themselves, where, along with potassium, it is the second most important mineral. Only 1% of magnesium is found in the blood. It is a macronutrient, a natural calcium antagonist and a regulator of vascular tone, blood pressure and peripheral circulation [1].

Magnesium activates ATPase, an essential enzyme for the functioning of the cell membrane and an energy source for the Na–K pump. Intracellular magnesium deficiency can cause an increase in cellular sodium and calcium content and a decrease in potassium content [1]. Despite the important role of magnesium, its level is rarely determined, although in one study hypomagnesemia was detected in 42% of hospitalized patients, hypermagnesemia in 6% [2].

At the same time, the level of magnesium, like potassium, in the blood serum often remains normal, despite a decrease in its content in the body. In general, neither the serum level nor the determination of the intracellular content of magnesium gives a true picture of its physiological activity, in contrast to the determination of free magnesium, which is possible using magnetic resonance imaging [3]. However, in clinical practice, only determination of serum magnesium levels is available. Despite the fact that almost all magnesium is found intracellularly in the body, low serum levels correlate with general magnesium deficiency [4].

Conducted epidemiological studies indicate that serum magnesium levels are inversely associated with risk factors for cardiovascular diseases, such as arterial hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus, metabolic syndrome, as well as with the presence of coronary heart disease [5].

Other evidence from environmental studies, clinical studies, and autopsies suggests that increasing magnesium levels potentially protects against cardiovascular disease [6].

The physiological role of magnesium in the body

Magnesium influences the regulation of biochemical processes in the body through magnesium-containing enzymes and free magnesium ions (being a

cofactor in many enzymatic reactions (hydrolysis and transfer of phosphate groups, the functioning of the Na⁺–K⁺–ATP pump, Ca²⁺–ATP pump, proton pump, participates in the exchange of electrolytes, hydrolysis ATP, reduces the separation of oxidation and phosphorylation, regulates glycolysis and the oxidation of fatty acids; is involved in protein biosynthesis, the transfer of genetic information, the synthesis of cyclic AMP and the synthesis of nitric oxide in the vascular endothelium).

In addition, magnesium is involved in maintaining the electrical balance of the cell (including in the process of depolarization; with a lack of magnesium, the cell becomes overexcitable).

Magnesium has an inhibitory effect on the conduction of nerve impulses, is part of numerous enzymes of nervous and glial tissues, is involved in the processes of synthesis and degradation of neurotransmitters (norepinephrine, acetylcholine), as well as in the regulation of neuromuscular activity of conducting tissues of the body (cardiac muscle, skeletal muscles, smooth muscles of internal organs), since it prevents the entry of calcium ions through the presynaptic membrane, which determines the presence of myotropic, antispasmodic and disaggregation effects.

This element is a component of the antioxidant system, an important component of the immune system. It inhibits premature involution of the thymus, regulates the phagocytic activity of macrophages, the interaction of T- and B-lymphocytes.

Being next to calcium in the group of the periodic table, magnesium is a calcium antagonist: these two elements easily displace each other from compounds. Magnesium deficiency in a diet rich in calcium causes calcium retention in all tissues, which leads to their calcification [7].

Magnesium enters the body with food (in particular table salt) and water. The intake rate is usually 200–400 mg per day. Plant foods are especially rich in magnesium: legumes and cereals, spinach, salads, nuts. However, the magnesium content in them can vary significantly depending on the growing soil. Water is also an important source, and the harder it is, the higher its magnesium content. In regions with soft water, the incidence of hypomagnesemia is high. Part of the ionized magnesium is split off from the magnesium salts of food in the stomach and absorbed into the blood. The main part of the sparingly soluble magnesium salts passes into the intestines and is absorbed only after they are combined with fatty acids. Up to 40–45% of incoming magnesium is absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract. In human blood, about 50% of magnesium is in a bound state, and the rest is ionized. The concentration of magnesium in human blood is 2.3–4.0 mg. Complex magnesium compounds enter the liver, where they are used for the synthesis of biologically active compounds. The main “depot” of magnesium is in bones and muscles. Magnesium is excreted from the body mainly through urine (50–120 mg) and sweat (5–15 mg). The absorption of magnesium increases with its deficiency in the body. For absorption, a sufficient amount of cofactors must be supplied to the body: lactic, aspartic, orotic acids and vitamin B6. Vitamins B1, B6, C, D, E, calcium, phosphorus (available in optimal

quantities), protein, estrogens help increase magnesium levels in the body [7]. Magnesium is excreted primarily by the kidneys, also through sweating.

The causes of magnesium deficiency may be:

- insufficient supply (regions with “soft” water”);
- malabsorption in the intestine (dysbacteriosis, chronic duodenitis);
- dysregulation of magnesium metabolism;
- decreased absorption due to excess phosphates, calcium and lipids;
- long-term use of antibiotics (gentamicin), diuretics, antitumor and other pharmacological drugs;
- parenteral nutrition;
- increased need for magnesium (during pregnancy, during the period of growth and recovery, chronic alcoholism, excessive sweating);
- disruption of insulin synthesis;
- intoxication with aluminum, beryllium, lead, nickel, cadmium, cobalt and manganese.

Magnesium deficiency is the most common type of mineral deficiency in the population in many countries, particularly in the United States. Main manifestations of magnesium deficiency:

- fatigue, irritability;
- insomnia disorders, dizziness;
- loss of appetite, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, constipation;
- cardialgia, palpitations, fluctuations in blood pressure (BP), prolongation of the QT interval;
- arrhythmias, vasospasms, muscle weakness, muscle cramps;
- immunodeficiencies (possibly increased risk of tumor diseases);
- bronchospasm and laryngospasm;
- paresthesia, smooth muscle spasms.

Magnesium deficiency, increasing uterine contractility, can provoke premature birth.

Increased magnesium content in the body

The main causes of excess magnesium: excess intake; Dysregulation of magnesium metabolism. An increase in magnesium concentration is observed with hyperfunction of the parathyroid glands, thyroid gland, nephrocalcinosis, arthritis, psoriasis, dyslexia (a disorder with impaired understanding of readable text in children). Magnesium salt, when administered orally, even in large doses, does not cause poisoning, but acts only as a laxative. At the same time, with parenteral administration of magnesium sulfate, symptoms of intoxication may be observed in the form of general depression, lethargy and drowsiness. With a significant overdose of magnesium compounds, there may be a risk of poisoning (for example, with antacids). Anesthesia occurs when magnesium concentrations in the blood are 15–18 mg%.

The role of magnesium in the pathogenesis of various diseases of the cardiovascular system

It was found that during postmortem assessment of magnesium content in patients who died from ischemic heart disease, the magnesium level was lower

than in patients who died from other causes. Several studies have shown that patients who have suffered a myocardial infarction are significantly more likely to have magnesium deficiency, but it is not known whether it was a cause or a consequence of the disease [8]. Some, although not all, studies have shown improved survival of patients with myocardial infarction with magnesium therapy [9].

A recently completed study assessing the correlation between magnesium levels and sudden cardiac death found a significant reduction in the risk of sudden cardiac death with increasing serum magnesium levels, independent of other factors such as hypertension, diabetes, potassium levels, heart rate, and history of coronary artery disease. However, no connection has been established between the level of magnesium intake and the risk of sudden cardiac death [10]. However, in relation to arterial hypertension and coronary artery disease, a connection was also previously established with serum magnesium concentration, and not with its consumption [11]. It has been revealed that a reduced magnesium content in drinking water increases the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases (especially coronary heart disease) and sudden death [12].

Atherosclerosis and dyslipidemia

There is evidence of a relationship between magnesium deficiency and atherosclerosis. It has been shown that magnesium deficiency is associated with an increase in the level of total cholesterol, low-density lipids, triglycerides, a decrease in the activity of lecithin-cholesterol-aminotransferase and lipoprotein lipase, and an increase in the activity of SMC-COA reductase [13]. Several animal experiments have shown that supplemental magnesium, even in combination with an atherogenic diet, slowed the progression of atherosclerosis compared with controls, regardless of cholesterol levels. In some studies among patients with hyperlipidemia, a positive significant effect was obtained in reducing the level of total cholesterol and its atherogenic fractions. In addition, several risk factors, such as hypertension, obesity, insulin resistance, have a common denominator - magnesium deficiency.

Diabetes

Magnesium deficiency is important in the pathogenesis of diabetes for several reasons: many enzymes involved in the process of glycolysis are magnesium-dependent. In both insulin-dependent and non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus, magnesium deficiency was detected in the serum, intracellularly, as well as increased urinary excretion [14]. In addition, it was shown that the degree of diabetes control was directly related to the degree of magnesium deficiency, and supplemental magnesium intake was associated with improved diabetes control. However, not all people with diabetes have hypomagnesemia, and the degree of hypomagnesemia varies depending on the type of diabetes and gender [15].

Arterial hypertension

Magnesium deficiency may play a role in the pathogenesis of hypertension, another risk factor for coronary heart disease. Magnesium is involved in the activation of the Na-K-ATP pump and also regulates the entry of calcium into the

cell. Thus, magnesium deficiency can lead to a decrease in intracellular sodium and calcium content, an increase in total peripheral resistance and vasospasm, as found in experimental studies in animals.

A number of studies have found an association with the intake of certain macronutrients, including magnesium, and hypertension [16]. However, the importance of magnesium in the pathogenesis of hypertension is not completely clear, since various studies have reported conflicting results when examining the relationship between intake, excretion, serum magnesium levels and the degree of hypertension. A systematic review concluded that there is currently insufficient evidence to make a definitive judgment on the relationship between magnesium and hypertension [17].

However, for certain categories of patients with hypertension, impaired magnesium metabolism is definitely important. In particular, it has been established that with a family history of hypertension, there is a reduced intracellular magnesium content. In addition, the hypotensive effect of additional magnesium intake was noted in patients with reduced urinary excretion, in contrast to other categories of patients, where there was no hypotensive effect [18].

Patients with high plasma renin levels had reduced plasma magnesium levels and responded better to magnesium supplementation. An inverse relationship has been established between the levels of aldosterone and plasma renin, which indicates that low magnesium levels are associated with increased activity of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system [19].

Once satisfactory control of arterial hypertension is achieved, the level of free magnesium is normalized. When taking non-potassium-sparing diuretics for antihypertensive purposes, significant hypomagnesemia also often occurs. Supplemental magnesium helps eliminate it, improving hypertension control [20].

Spasm of the coronary arteries

Magnesium can be considered a natural calcium channel blocker, since as a coenzyme it is involved in the movement of calcium into and out of smooth muscle cells. The importance of hypomagnesemia in the development of spasm and the effectiveness of intravenous administration of magnesium in its elimination has been confirmed both in vitro and in vivo experiments. Finally, intravenous administration of magnesium sulfate for vasospastic angina helps to effectively eliminate vasospasm, which once again confirms the importance of magnesium deficiency in the development of coronary spasm [21].

Myocardial infarction

The state of magnesium metabolism in the period preceding the development of myocardial infarction is difficult to assess, for obvious reasons: the available data are contradictory. However, it is clearly established that after a myocardial infarction, hypomagnesemia occurs, which persists for up to 6 months. A meta-analysis of several controlled trials showed that with magnesium infusion, the mortality rate in the treatment group was 3.8% compared with the control group, where this figure was 8%. The main effect is the elimination of malignant arrhythmias [22, 25]. Most studies have found a correlation between hypomagnesemia and post-infarction ventricular arrhythmias.

Chronic heart failure

The development of hypomagnesemia in heart failure is explained by several factors. Due to an increase in the volume of extracellular fluid and the development of secondary hyperaldosteronism, magnesium absorption decreases. In addition, non-potassium-sparing diuretics also promote the excretion of magnesium. In turn, hypomagnesemia aggravates hyperaldosteronism, which leads to fluid retention, can reduce myocardial contractility, and increases vasoconstriction. Hypomagnesemia in combination with hypokalemia contributes to the occurrence of ventricular arrhythmias. However, not all researchers recognize the importance and prevalence of hypomagnesemia in heart failure; it has only been clearly established that active diuretic therapy leads to hypomagnesemia and this occurs in more than half of patients [23].

Arrhythmias

Since magnesium is involved in the transport of sodium, potassium and calcium, changes in its concentration affect the exchange of electrolytes and the processes of electrical excitation of the cell. The best known relationship is between hypokalemia and hypomagnesemia. An increase in magnesium levels leads to bradycardia, increased conduction time and suppression of automaticity.

Magnesium deficiency, which is often accompanied by hypokalemia, causes prolongation of the QT interval, depression of the ST segment and low-amplitude T waves. Magnesium combines a membrane-stabilizing effect and the properties of a calcium antagonist, reduces the variability of the duration of the QT interval, which is an unfavorable prognostic factor for the development of fatal arrhythmias. In addition, magnesium is able to inhibit sympathetic influences on the heart [24].

The effectiveness of intravenous administration of magnesium in stopping ventricular extrasystole has been identified for a long time, not only in patients with hypokalemia, but also with normal levels of magnesium in plasma. The Framingham study demonstrated the relationship between hypomagnesemia and an increased incidence of ventricular extrasystoles, tachycardia, and ventricular fibrillation. In the PROMISE study, in the group of patients with hypomagnesemia, greater mortality and a higher incidence of ventricular extrasystoles were noted compared with the group with normal plasma magnesium levels [25].

Многие годы магний в виде сульфата эффективно применяются в купировании пируэтной желудочковой тахикардии, его эффект обусловлен угнетением следовых деполяризаций и укорочением длительности интервала QT [26].

For supraventricular arrhythmias, magnesium infusion often transforms supraventricular tachyarrhythmias (atrial tachycardia, polyfocal atrial tachycardia) into sinus rhythm. Moreover, this category of patients often exhibits hypomagnesemia or concomitant use of loop diuretics, digoxin, aminoglycosides - drugs that promote hypomagnesemia.

The mechanism of influence on arrhythmias caused by digitalis intoxication remains unclear. Magnesium may work by blocking potassium or calcium channels or restoring potassium-sodium pump function. With digitalis intoxication, hypomagnesemia occurs much more often than without it; among patients on

digoxin therapy, hypomagnesemia is detected in every fifth. Moreover, magnesium administration is effective both in patients with hypomagnesemia and in patients with normal magnesium levels [27].

In general, the results of the randomized multicenter placebo-controlled double-blind study MAGICA allowed us to consider magnesium and potassium preparations as the generally accepted European standard for the treatment of arrhythmias in patients taking cardiac glycosides, diuretics, and antiarrhythmics. The antiarrhythmic effect of magnesium drugs appears after 3 weeks from the start of treatment and allows you to reduce the number of ventricular extrasystoles by 12% and the total number of extrasystoles by 60–70% [24].

Mitral valve prolapse

According to epidemiological studies, in patients with mitral valve prolapse, as well as other congenital connective tissue dysplasias, magnesium deficiency is detected in almost 2/3 of cases, which is associated with impaired collagen synthesis against the background of magnesium deficiency [28].

Conclusion. Magnesium deficiency may play a significant role in the pathogenesis of coronary artery disease, some types of arrhythmias, and sudden cardiac death, but how clinicians should use this information in daily practice remains unclear. However, even with normal plasma magnesium levels, the patient may suffer from hypomagnesemia. Since many of these patients are taking diuretics for hypertension or heart failure, in many cases it is advisable to add potassium-sparing diuretics to therapy, which also promote magnesium retention. In hospital settings, patients with documented hypomagnesemia should use magnesium preparations intravenously, intramuscularly or orally depending on the clinical situation.

Thus, magnesium preparations play an important role in the management of patients with cardiovascular pathology, primarily due to their ability to favorably influence existing risk factors and reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases at the population level.

In case of magnesium deficiency, its additional administration is required at the rate of 10–30 mg per 1 kg of body weight per day for at least 2 months, which is due to the slow saturation of tissue depots. It is impossible to ensure such an increased intake of magnesium only by changing the diet. It is necessary to use magnesium supplements.

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